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The EC/EU Autonomous Economic Sanctions as Tools of Geoeconomics

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DECLARATION OF HONOUR:

I declare that this thesis is my own work and that all references to or quotations from the work of others are fully and correctly cited.

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Summary

Liberalism theory highlights that a state's economic prosperity is crucial in shaping its national security in international relations. A country's ability to maintain national security is closely linked to its economic well-being. Any weakness in sustainable economic growth can hurt this ability.

This concept is evident in the 2017 National Security Strategy of the United States, which reiterates the significance of economic security as a critical component of national security. The document emphasises that the US should adopt a strategic and proactive approach to protect the country's economic and national interests. When it comes to achieving their political objectives, states often resort to using economic sanctions as a means to an end.

Recent research studies have shown that economic sanctions may unexpectedly impact the target country's trade volume. Inflation, a common phenomenon during economic sanctions, may increase trade volume between the sender and target countries, suggesting that economic sanctions can induce exchange rate volatility and inflation in the target country, which can benefit the sender's trade with the target. The target country's currency depreciates during inflation, making its exports cheaper. In turn, it makes the target country's exports more attractive to the sender country, which can increase trade volume.

This study analyses 14 autonomous economic sanctions in force in the European Union (EU) in 2021. The aim is to examine the total trade value of the EU with the targeted countries for three years while keeping all other factors constant (*ceteris paribus*). It seeks to identify any possible changes that may have occurred in the EU's trade volume with the targeted countries, which could serve as evidence for the earlier-mentioned statement.

The findings reveal that economic sanctions serve the EU's national interest by partly benefiting their trade and strengthening economic security, confirming that economic sanctions are a tool of geoeconomics.

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Chapter I: Introduction

Following the collapse of the Iron Curtain, a new perspective on International Relations emerged, known as Liberalism. This approach greatly emphasises a state's economic prosperity as a determining factor in its national security (Kenneth, 1985). Within the framework of IR Liberalism, economic sanctions can serve a dual purpose. They act as a means of punishing the target nation while also playing a critical role in maintaining economic stability to ensure the sender country's national security.

The National Security Strategy of the United States in 2017 emphasised the significance of economic security as a fundamental element of national security. This categorisation has highlighted that economic sanctions are used as a tool by countries to safeguard their geopolitical and national interests and play a crucial role in ensuring economic security.

Economic sanctions significantly advance national policies through their impact on trade policies. The effectiveness of economic sanctions lies in their ability to restrict the targeted country's access to the global market and financial systems, which can significantly impact the economic growth and development of the target country. Therefore, the effective use of economic sanctions can contribute to ensuring overall national security and play a vital role in the economic security of a country.

According to several studies, countries often impose sanctions based on the sender's political and economic factors rather than the behaviour of the targeted country (Drury, 2005; Waelder, 1997; Kaempfer and Lowenberg, 2009). Researchers have found that interest groups play a significant role in determining the severity of the sanctions imposed by the sender country (Belin and Hanousek, 2021). Typically, a sender country imposes sanctions due to the concerns of politically influential interest groups within their own country. These sanctions usually target politically influential groups within the target country. However, the sending country must consider the expected gains and costs before imposing sanctions, as export sanctions can result in a loss of foreign markets. In contrast, import sanctions can create new markets for domestic producers (Brooks, 2002).

Jones and Portela's (2014) research suggests that countries can impose unilateral and autonomous sanctions to benefit their domestic economy and promote local businesses if the objectives align with their interests. Various factors, including the influence of interest groups and political fundraising requirements, can trigger sanctions. However, sanctions can also be wielded by leading factions within the sender state to achieve their socio-political and ideological goals, maintain domestic stability, or prepare the public for possible conflicts. In such cases, sanctions can be a means to an end rather than an end in themselves. (Preeg, 1999; Drury, 2000; Fisk, 2000; Fayazmanesh, 2004 (sic); Gordon, 2010; Van Bergeijk, 1995; Kaempfer and Lowenbrug, 1992; Helms, 1999; Barber, 1979, in Jones and Portela, 2014).

According to the latest research, economic sanctions imposed on a country can increase trade value. Such sanctions often lead to a significant rise in exchange rate volatility and inflation. As a result, traders tend to take advantage of this situation by increasing their trade activities and exploiting the fluctuating exchange rates. This trend has been observed in several countries that have been subject to economic sanctions in recent years (Wang et al., 2019; Belin and Hanousek, 2021).

Import sanctions can reduce a country's exports and lead to financial difficulties, prompting the sender to import products from the target country at a lower cost than before, potentially increasing their imports from the target (*ceteris paribus*).

Export sanctions reduce supply to the target country, increasing the cost of imported raw materials, leading to currency depreciation, volatility in exchange rates, and higher import costs. As a result, the value of sender exports to the target country increases (*ceteris paribus*).

Financial sanctions limit investments and transactions, forcing target countries to rely on central banks and increasing inflation and exchange rate fluctuations. Lack of foreign currency reserves drives demand for solid currencies like the USD and Euro, strengthening the sender's currency.

The primary objectives of the present study are:

- to examine the total value of the sender's trade with the target during the last three years and
- to determine the generalisability of the findings.

The objective of this study is to analyse to either confirm or disprove the hypotheses presented in the works of Jones and Portela (2014), Wang et al. (2019), Brooks (2002), Drury (2005), Waelder (1997), Kaempfer and Lowenberg (2007) and Belin and Hanousek (2011). The focus is on evaluating the theories and their relevance in the context of the research subject.

This research endeavour contributes significantly to the existing literature by investigating the plausible association between exchange rate volatility and inflation, which emanates from the ramifications of economic sanctions. The study aims to shed light on the potential impact of exchange rate fluctuations on inflation in the context of economic sanctions. The results of this study help scholars better understand the effects of economic sanctions on exchange rate volatility and inflation, thereby contributing to expanding the existing literature on the effects of autonomous economic sanctions.

The following research questions may help to address the identified research gap:

RQ1: Do the EU autonomous economic sanctions in force in 2021 have an economic impact on the sender?

RQ2: What is the economic impact of EU autonomous economic sanctions in force in 2021 on the sender's trade with the target?

RQ3: In which way do the sanctions impact the target country?

The set of research questions that have been formulated is designed to play a pivotal role in either supporting or rejecting the hypotheses that have been put forward for consideration. By providing detailed and comprehensive answers to these questions, the research can provide a clear and concise evaluation of the hypotheses and their potential validity. This would help further understand the subject matter and develop more accurate and evidence-based conclusions.

H1. Most EU autonomous economic sanctions in force in 2021 may positively impact the sender's trade with the target.

H2. EU autonomous economic sanctions serve, in part, the national interest by securing the senders' economic security.

H3. Economic sanctions are a tool of geoeconomics serving the sender's national security.

This research's primary objective is to comprehensively analyse an original dataset encompassing fourteen EU autonomous economic sanctions in force in 2021. The dataset has been meticulously created by gathering data from reliable EU government sources (data triangulation) and existing studies on the subject (investigator triangulation). The aim is to use comparative and descriptive analysis techniques to provide plausible arguments for whether these sanctions have a discernible economic impact on the sender.

This research delves deep into the intricate details of the original dataset, examining each sanction individually and comparing their economic impact on the sender. The analysis will consider various factors, such as the type and duration of the sanction, the targeted industry, and the economic relationship between the sender and the target.

The research comprises a comprehensive five-chapter document, each chapter playing a specific role in presenting the findings and conclusions of the study.

Chapter I provides an overview of the research background, highlighting the key issues the study aims to address. In Chapter II, the methodology and data used in the research are described in detail. Chapter III is dedicated to presenting the research results clearly and concisely. The discussion surrounding the findings is presented in Chapter IV, while Chapter V thoroughly summarises the conclusions reached in relation to the central research questions and hypotheses.

Chapter II: Methodology and Data

This research study incorporates both qualitative and quantitative research methods, along with comparative and descriptive analysis techniques. A theoretical model is utilised in conjunction with an original data set containing 14 EU-sanction episodes that were currently active in 2021. The study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the nature of these episodes through a detailed analysis of the collected data.

In order to accomplish the primary aim of this study, I examine the volume of trade initiated by the sender (in billions of dollars or euros) with the recipient over three years. Considering the total value of the sender's exports and imports to and from the target country over the same time frame may ensure that events before the sanctions' imposition do not impact the reported values.

Sanctions on imports can cause inflation, exchange rate instability, and reduced exports for the target country. However, the sender's currency may become more valuable, making possible cheaper imports from the target country. Analysing the sender's trade value with the target may reveal increased imports from the target country due to lower prices (*ceteris paribus*).

Export sanctions can increase the price of imports and lead to currency depreciation, which may result in the target country paying a higher price for imports from the sender country (*ceteris paribus*).

Restricting financial transactions within a country can lead to reliance on domestic central banks, causing inflation and benefiting the sender's currency. Insufficient foreign currency reserves can result in higher global market rates and strengthen the sender's currency, contributing to inflation in the target country. Consequently, the sender can import affordably from the target while exporting goods at higher prices (*Ceteris paribus*).

Thus, this research tests the following assumptions:

- (1) The sender's imports from the target for three years should be higher than the total value of the sender's imports and exports from the target country (*ceteris paribus*) before imposing sanctions.
- (2). The sender's exports to the target for three years should be higher than the total value of the sender's imports and exports from the target country (*ceteris paribus*) before imposing sanctions.
- (3). The total value of the sender's trade (export and import) with the target for three years should be higher than the total value of the sender's trade with the target country (*ceteris paribus*) before imposing sanctions.

In light of this scenario, assuming all other factors remain constant, it can be inferred that the imposition of sanctions has resulted in a positive outcome in their economic association with the targeted entity.

This particular research methodology is designed to enable the direct observation of the effects of sanctions on targeted countries without interference from other variables that could potentially obscure the true impact of the sanctions. Such variables may include policy outcomes, the impact of globalisation, technological advancements, consumer behaviour, increasing competition, or fluctuations in consumer welfare.

This approach allows for a clear and unobstructed view of the dynamics that are induced by sanctions on the targeted countries. By eliminating the influence of extraneous factors, the methodology provides a comprehensive understanding of the true impact of sanctions on the targeted countries.

The credibility and reliability of this study on trade growth are ensured by relying on official databases. To further enhance the accuracy of the findings, documented sanctions events are also considered. This approach provides a more thorough and precise analysis, eliminating any ambiguities that could potentially affect the results.

When studying the impact of sanctions on trade volume with a particular country, it is crucial to eliminate the influence of other economic factors such as consumer welfare, policy outcomes, globalisation, technology, and competition. By doing so, it can obtain precise and reliable results that accurately reflect the true effect of sanctions on trade volume with the target country. This approach enables gaining a deeper understanding of the economic implications of sanctions based on reliable and accurate data.

The 'sanction types' consist of financial sanctions (F) = suspending aid, commercial, and official finance; export sanctions (X) = banning senders' exports to the target; and import sanctions (M) = prohibiting imports from the targeted country.

This research bases on literature written by several reputable authors. These include Kenneth (1985), Drury (2005), Waelder (1997), Kaempfer and Lowenberg (2007), Belin and Hanousek (2021), Brook (2002), Jones and Portela (2014), and Wang et al. (2019). In addition, data is sourced and analysed from several internationally recognised databases, including the EC Directorate-General for Trade (2021), World Integrated Trade Solution (2021), EU Sanctions Map (2021), and Country Economy (2021). The study aims to provide a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the subject matter by drawing on multiple sources of information and analysis.

This study uses a unique dataset, which sets this research apart from previous studies. This research focuses on examining the implications and effectiveness of these sanctions in detail. As such, this study presents an original analysis of the EU's autonomous sanctions framework that has not been explored before. The findings of this research will contribute to the existing literature and provide insights into the efficacy of autonomous sanctions as a policy tool.

Chapter III: Results

The results of this study base on the analysis of 14 EU autonomous sanctions in force in 2021. These sanctions were intended to destabilise the target country's economy by creating an increase in exchange rate volatility and inflation. However, the findings suggest that in almost 79% of cases (11 out of 14), trade between the sender and the targeted country increased within three years. In the cases of Guinea (09-2), Myanmar (13-2), and Venezuela (17-1), the EU saw a decrease in the import and export volume to and from those targeted countries.

Table 1: The EU import and export volume from/to sanctioned countries in 2021

	Targeted country	Period of time	Type of sanction	Total EU imports at the beginning of the period of time Value Mio €	Total EU imports at the end of the period of time Value Mio €	Difference Value Mio €	Difference in %	Total EU exports at the beginning of the period of time Value Mio €	Total EU exports at the end of the period of time Value Mio €	Difference Value Mio €	Difference in %
1	China (89-1)	2019-2021	F, X	363 461	472 762	109 301	30,07	198 486	223 571	25 085	12,64
2	Zimbabwe (02-1)	2019-2021	F, X	359	399	40	11,14	151	186	35	23,18
3	Guinea (09-2)	2019-2021	F	736	465	-271	-36,82	946	835	-111	-11,73
4	Bosnia-Herzegovina (11-1)	2019-2021	F	4 379	5 838	1 459	33,32	6 313	6 842	529	8,38
5	Iran (11-3)	2019-2021	F, X, M	680	922	242	35,59	4 398	3 940	-458	-10,41
6	Tunisia (11-6)	2019-2021	F	10 019	10 262	243	2,43	10 939	10 838	-101	-0,92
7	Belarus (12-1)	2019-2021	F, X	4 174	5 954	1 780	42,64	6 694	6 931	237	3,54
8	Myanmar (13-2)	2019-2021	F, X	2 813	2 249	-564	-20,05	608	322	-286	-47,04
9	Syria (13-3)	2019-2021	F, X, M	59	61	2	3,39	598	304	-294	-49,16
10	Russia (14-1)	2019-2021	F, X, M	144 942	162 542	17 600	12,14	87 755	89 272	1 517	1,73
11	Ukraine (14-2)	2019-2021	F, X, M	19 139	24 053	4 914	25,68	24 153	28 291	4 138	17,13
12	Venezuela (17-1)	2019-2021	F, X	2 217	535	-1 682	-75,87	696	371	-325	-46,70
13	Nicaragua (19-1)	2019-2021	F	345	341	-4	-1,16	186	214	28	15,05
14	Turkey (19-2)	2019-2021	F	69 812	77 963	8 151	11,68	68 260	79 266	11 006	16,12

Source: own table based EC Directorate-General for Trade (2021), World Integrated Trade Solution (2021), EU Sanctions Map (2021).

Note: F = financial sanctions, X = export sanctions, M= import sanctions.

Note: Each case has an identification number from the year it was imposed, and the consecutive number of sanctions set that year.

Most of the EU sanctions in 2021 were a mix of various sanctions.

Most of the financial and export sanctions (F, X) (five episodes) partially confirmed the expected findings, as the EU's import and export volume with the targeted countries increased (China (89-1), Zimbabwe (02-1), and Belarus (12-1)). However, the sanctions against Myanmar (13-2) and Venezuela (17-1) did not yield the expected outcomes.

The research results on financial, export, and import sanctions (F, X, M) (four episodes) have only partially confirmed the initial expectations. The trade volume between the sender and the target country increased only in two cases: Russia (14-1) and Ukraine (14-2). However, in the cases of Iran (11-3) and Syria (11-4), the export volume increased while the import volume decreased.

Regarding financial sanctions (F) (five episodes), most of them fulfilled the expectations. The sender's import and export volume increased in two sanction episodes: Bosnia Herzegovina (11-1) and Turkey (19-2). The sanctions against Nicaragua (19-1) decreased EU imports and increased EU export volume to the target. In the case of Guinea (09-1), import and export volume decreased. Please observe that the visual representation of the findings is available for review in Table 2.

Table 2: Type of sanction used by the EU autonomous sanctions in force in 2021

Type of sanction	EU Imports (M)		EU exports (X)	
	imports (M) increase	imports (M) decrease	exports (X) increase	exports (X) decrease
Financial (F) (5 episodes)		Guinea (09-1)		Guinea (09-1)
	Bosnia Herzegovina (11-1)		Bosnia Herzegovina (11-1)	
	Tunisia (11-5)			Tunisia (11-5)
		Nicaragua (19-1)	Nicaragua (19-1)	
	Turkey (19-2)		Turkey (19-2)	
Financial and Export (F,X) (5 episodes)	China (89-1)		China (89-1)	
	Zimbabwe (02-1)		Zimbabwe (02-1)	
	Belarus (12-1)		Belarus (12-1)	
		Myanmar (13-2)		Myanmar (13-2)
		Venezuela (17-1)		Venezuela (17-1)
Financial, export and import (F,X,M) (4 episodes)	Iran (11-3)			Iran (11-3)
	Syria** (11-4)			Syria** (11-4)
	Russia (14-1)		Russia /14-1)	
	Ukraine (14-2)		Ukraine (14-2)	

Source: own table based on EC Directorate-General for Trade (2023), World Integrated Trade Solution (2023), EU Sanctions Map (2023).

Note: Each case has an identification number from the year it was imposed, and the consecutive number of sanctions set that year.

** Multiple sanctions simultaneously.

Chapter IV: Discussion

The findings reveal that most EU sanctions (about 79%) in force in 2021 may positively impact the sender's trade with the target country. This suggests that the sanctions were effective in fact as the EU's trade volume with the targeted countries increased. This suggests that those sanctions were effective from an international relations point of view. However, it appears that the rest of the sanctions were able to achieve the economic security goals of the sender.

The sanctions were mainly a combination of different types of sanctions. The EU's import and export volume increased in most of the nine instances where these combined sanctions were applied. However, in two cases, only the EU's import volume increased; in two others, the EU's trade volume with the targets decreased.

Sanctions are a commonly used tool in international relations to exert economic pressure on other countries and have various effects on the targeted country's economy, including causing inflation and exchange rate fluctuations, which can impact trade volume.

When import sanctions are imposed, the targeted country's ability to export goods to the sender's country is reduced. This results in a decrease in supply, which can raise the prices of goods, leading to inflation. However, the reduction in exports can also cause the targeted country's currency to appreciate in value, making it more valuable than the sender's currency. On the other hand, export sanctions reduce the targeted country's ability to import goods from the sender's country. This can lead to a decrease in demand and a subsequent decrease in the prices of goods, causing inflation. However, the reduction in imports can also cause the targeted country's currency to depreciate in value, making it less valuable relative to the sender's currency. Limiting financial transactions can also contribute to inflation. This is because it can make it more difficult for the targeted country to access foreign currency, which can drive up the value of the sender's currency relative to the targeted country's currency. This, in turn, can cause inflation in the targeted country.

The effects of sanctions on a country's economy are multifaceted and complex. While sanctions can effectively achieve political objectives, they can also have economic consequences on the targeted country's economy and its citizens. One effective strategy is to leverage sanctions to increase the sender's trade with the target country, thereby increasing economic security, which is a crucial component of national security, as stated in the US National Security Strategy 2017.

The study's results indicated that the EU's trade with the target nations experienced a notable increase. These target countries included China (89-1) by 11.60%, Zimbabwe (02-1) by 20.50%; Bosnia Herzegovina (11-1) by 25%, Belarus (12-1) by 13.50%, Ukraine (14-2) by 24.30%, Nicaragua (19-1) by 27.90% and Turkey (19-2) by 12.90%.

The AMA/NAMA Product Groups, which is a classification system used by the EU, shows that the majority of the EU's exported goods were industrial products. This suggests that the EU's economy has a strong manufacturing and production base, which is reflected in its export volume.

In 2021, despite the explicit arms embargo, the EU's arms and ammunition exports to China (89-1) increased by 5.10% and to Russia (14-1) by 54.30%. The EU's export volume on arms and ammunition to Ukraine (14-2) increased by 70% (European Commission, European Union, Trade in goods 2021)

At the same time, most EU import volume increased in the industrial products: China (89-1) by 22.90%, Zimbabwe (02-1) by 9.70%, Bosnia Herzegovina (11-1) by 44.40%, Iran (11-3) by 45.70%, Tunisia (11-6) by 21.60%, Belarus (12-1) by 52.30%, Syria (13-3) by 20.80%, Russia (14-1) by 73%, Ukraine (14-2) by 63.20%, and Turkey (19-2) by 26.40% (European Commission, European Union, Trade in goods 2021).

The AMA/NAMA Product Groups classification of industrial products is a comprehensive framework that categorizes various types of products. This classification encompasses a broad range of products such as mineral products, products of the chemical or allied industries, plastic and rubber products and their articles, pulp of wood, paper and paperboard products, machinery and appliances, transportation equipment, optical and photographic instruments, arms, and ammunition. This detailed classification system helps to identify and differentiate industrial products, making it easier to manage and track their production, trade, and consumption.

The EU has a considerable difference between the volume of industrial products it imports and exports from a targeted country. This difference is significant and has a considerable impact on the EU's economic relationship with the targeted country. The EU's sanctions against the targeted country resulted in inflation, which caused the currency of the target country to devalue. This devaluation strengthened the currency of the sender country, enabling them to import more products from the target country at a lower price. As a result, the EU was able to import raw materials at a reduced cost and produce finished products at a higher price than before the sanctions.

In conclusion, the EU's sanctions had a significant impact on the target country's economy, leading to inflation and currency devaluation. However, the EU benefited from the sanctions, as it allowed them to import raw materials at a lower price and export finished products at a higher price. Consequently, the findings prove that autonomous EU sanctions may increase the sender's trading volume with the target by leveraging the target's inflation caused by the sanctions.

This study, conducted on EU autonomous economic sanctions in force in 2021, reveals interesting findings on EU's autonomous sanctions. Firstly, the research indicates that most of these sanctions can have a positive impact on trade between the sender and target countries. This suggests that the sanctions are an effective tool for achieving the desired outcome of promoting trade between nations.

Secondly, the study also found that these sanctions can serve the national interest of the EU. This is because they can improve trade relations with other countries, thereby strengthening the economy of the EU. This finding confirms the importance of economic sanctions as a tool of geoeconomics, which is the use of economic power to achieve strategic objectives.

In conclusion, the study highlights the effectiveness of economic sanctions in achieving trade-related objectives. The findings reveal that these sanctions can benefit both parties involved and serve the national interests of the EU. Therefore, it is important for policymakers to consider economic sanctions as a viable tool for promoting trade and achieving strategic objectives.

Chapter V: Conclusion

This particular research aims to expand the current knowledge on the subject of autonomous and unilateral sanctions within the domains of economic and international relations. The study focuses on the analysis of 14 cases of autonomous sanctions that were imposed by the European Union (EU). The main objective of this research is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the economic impact of such sanctions on the trade between the sender and target countries.

The study's findings suggest that implementing autonomous sanctions may have a positive effect on the sender's economy, leading to increased trade and economic growth. However, the research also acknowledges that the impact of such sanctions could vary depending on the nature of the targeted goods, the duration of the sanctions, and the level of dependence of the sender's economy on the target country.

Overall, this research contributes significantly to the existing literature on autonomous and unilateral sanctions. The findings of this study can be used to inform as well scholars and policymakers about the potential impact of sanctions on the sender's economy.

The study validates the theory that unilateral sanctions with sender-related goals can positively influence the sender's trade (Jones and Portela, 2014) by increasing the target's exchange rate volatility and inflation (Wang et al., 2019). Significantly, the findings regarding the export sanctions link the imposition of sanctions with the sender's trade surpluses, which can result in domestic policy pressure to impose import sanctions for creating new markets for domestic producers and validate the existing theories (Brooks, 2002; Drury, 2005; Waelder, 1997; Kaempfer and Lowenberg, 2007; Belin and Hanousek, 2021).

The research conducted on the imposition of sanctions has provided valuable insights into the sender's ability to enforce them endogenously. However, there is still much to be explored on the subject.

Future research can build on the existing findings to gain a deeper understanding of the various factors that affect the imposition of sanctions.

One such factor is the policy objectives behind the sanctions. It is important to investigate whether the sanctions were imposed to achieve specific political or economic goals. Additionally, the geographical location of the targeted country also plays a crucial role in the effectiveness of the sanctions.

Therefore, further research is necessary to determine how the location of the targeted country impacts the success or failure of the sanctions.

In summary, conducting additional research on the imposition of sanctions can provide a more comprehensive understanding of the subject. Investigating factors such as policy objectives and geographical location can help researchers develop a deeper understanding of how sanctions are enforced and, thereby, contribute to the development of more effective policies.

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